

Supplementary information for :

Newly described and already endangered: a new mammal species endemic to Corsica

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Table S2 – Primer information for nuclear introns amplified in the current study.

N, number of individuals in the alignment; bp, alignment length in base pairs; v, variable sites; pi, number of parsimony informative sites. Primers AAT amplify intron SLC38A7.

Primer	N	bp	v	pi	primer sequence	Substitution model	publication
AAT-F1	66	542	81	38	RGGCCTRGCYGSCTGCTTCATCTT	TPM2uf+G	Igea <i>et al.</i> (2010)
AAT-R1					TCVGASAGYTTGGCTTGRATGAGGCA		
ABHD11-F1	125	223	42	19	CTGCTCACCAACCTGGTGGAGGT	TrNef+G	Salicini <i>et al.</i> (2011)
ABHD11-R1					TTVGGCACRGTCTGCATCTGGGC		
ACOX2-F1	125	387	117	43	CCTSGGCTCDGAGGAGCAGAT	HKY+G	Salicini <i>et al.</i> (2011)
ACOX2-R1					GGGCTGTGHAYCACAAACTCCT		
COPS-F1	116	626	98	34	TACAGCATYGGRCGRGACATCCA	K80+G	Igea <i>et al.</i> (2010)
COPS-R1					TCACYTGCTCCTCRATGCCCKGACA		
ROGDI-F1	120	353	44	20	CTGATGGAYGCGYGTGATGCTGCA	TPM1	Salicini <i>et al.</i> (2011)
ROGDI-R1					CACGGTGAGGCASAGCTTGTTGA		

Table S3 – Microsatellite primer information.

M, multiplex. *these reverse primers were modified relative to the original publication by the addition of a pig-tail sequence to improve amplification specificity.

Locus	primer (μM)	M	primer publication	forward primer sequence	reverse primer sequence
D15	0.22	1	Castella and Ruedi (2000)	FAM-GCTCTCTGAAGAGGCCCTG	ATTCCAAGAGTGACAGCATCC
G30-Mluc	0.22	1	Jan <i>et al.</i> (2012)	FAM-GGCATGAACATGGAGTGAGG	*GTTT-GCTAGAAGTTATGGTCAATGTTCCCTG
H23-Mluc	0.16	1	Jan <i>et al.</i> (2012)	FAM-TTGTCTACTAGCATTGTCCAGTG	ATAGCTATGTTGCCTAACCTATTTACTC
EF15-Mluc	0.4	1	Jan <i>et al.</i> (2012)	NED-GATCGCAGTCCCTTCC	GCTTATGGGGAGAAATGAG
Mnatt-8	0.64	1	Scott <i>et al.</i> (2013)	VIC-ATCGCGAAAGTAAGGACAA	CTTTACCTCCAGTAGAATGTA
H29	0.64	1	Castella and Ruedi (2000)	FAM-TCAGGTGAGGATTGAAAACAC	GCTTTATTTAGCATTGGAGAGC
FV5AP	0.14	2	O' Donnell <i>et al.</i> (2016)	FAM-AACAGAGTTTGATGGGCTGTTAG	*GTTTT-TGAGGGTGCATGTGTAAGATTC
Paur06	0.48	2	Burland <i>et al.</i> (1998)	FAM-GATCAGATTTCCAAACAGAG	*GTTTCT-AGGTTCTTTCCTTCAGCTATG
b22	0.2	2	Kerth <i>et al.</i> (2002)	PET-CTGATGCAAGACCCCTTACAAC	*GTTTCT-ACGGCAGCAGTGAAATCAGA

Nuclear Intron Gene trees

SLC38A7 intron 8 (amplified by primers AAT)

Fig. S1. *Myotis* sp. gene tree for SLC38A7 intron 8 (amplified by primers AAT) 542 bp, n=66

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